

Final thesis for the Master's in Sound and Music Computing
Music Technology Group, Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Retrieving Ambiguous Sounds Using Perceptual Timbral Attributes in Audio Production Environments

Albin Andrew Correya

Supervisors: Dr. Frederic Font, Xavier Favory

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Dedication

I would like to dedicate this work to my loving parents for letting me dream, pursue and achieve what I have always wanted.

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Albin Andrew Correya

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Abstract

For over an decade, one of the well identified problem within audio production environments is the effective retrieval and management of sound libraries. Most of the self-recorded and commercially produced sound libraries are usually well structured in terms of meta-data and textual descriptions and thus allowing traditional text-based retrieval approaches to obtain satisfiable results. However, traditional information retrieval techniques pose limitations in retrieving ambiguous sound collections (ie. sounds with no identifiable origin, foley sounds, synthesized sound effects, abstract sounds) due to the difficulties in textual descriptions and the complex psychoacoustic nature of the sound. Early psychoacoustical studies propose perceptual acoustical qualities as an effective way of describing these category of sounds[1]. In Music Information Retrieval (MIR) studies, this problem were mostly studied and explored in context of content-based audio retrieval. However, we observed that most of the commercial available systems in the market neither integrated advanced content-based sound descriptions nor the visualization and interface design approaches evolved in the last years.

Our research was mainly aimed to investigate two things; 1. Development of audio retrieval system incorporating high level timbral features as search parameters. 2. Investigate user-centered approach in integrating these features into audio production pipelines using expert-user studies. In this project, We present an prototype which is similar to traditional sound browsers (list-based browsing) with an added functionality of filtering and ranking sounds by perceptual timbral features such as *brightness*, *depth*, *roughness* and *hardness*. Our main focus was on the retrieval process by timbral features. Inspiring from the recent focus on user-centered systems ([2], [3]) in the MIR community, in-depth interviews and qualitative evaluation of the system were conducted with expert-user in order to identify the underlying problems. Our studies observed the potential applications of high-level perceptual timbral features in audio production pipelines using a probe system and expert-user studies. We also outlined future guidelines and possible improvements to the system from the outcomes of this research.

Keywords: *Sound Browsers; Content-Based Audio Retrieval; Music Information Retrieval; Sound Databases; Audio Production; High-level Perceptual Timbral Features ; AudioCommons; User study ; Freesound*

Chapter 1

Introduction

The primary goal of any information retrieval (IR) system is to aid users to find their desired information from a collection of data. In audio production scenario, retrieval systems are supposed to help audio professionals in easing and aiding up their creative workflow. Traditional information retrieval researches and existing commercial systems for sound management focuses on using meaningful names, tags and meta-data descriptions of audio files in the retrieval process [4]. Even though in theory, this would be speed up the search process, the ambiguity and psychoacoustic nature of sound pose big hindrance in accomplishing satisfiable results. In the case of ambiguous sounds, which comprises sounds with no identifiable origin, synthesized sound effects and foley recordings, text based retrieval approaches are tend to be inefficient, especially if it's an unstructured database. People tends to define these kind of sounds in terms of abstract semantic concepts. An early survey of psychoacoustical studies [5] pointed out that sometimes these semantic concepts are related to the timbral attributes of sound. This also has been further investigated in Music Information Retrieval (MIR) studies. Audio retrieval and management is one of the extensively studied research topic in MIR researches. Most of these studies are based on the methodology of content-based audio retrieval, where certain meaningful features are computed from the audio itself to further classify or organize the sound collections. These computed features corresponds to various temporal and

spectral characteristics of sound[6]. However, from a user point-of-view, since these low-level features are not understandable and would confuse them in the retrieval process. This happens probably because the users to define timbral features with high-level semantic text terms. For example, the description *bright* sound is more clearer and understandable to user than saying sound with high *spectral centroid*[6] value . Identifying this, various efforts have been initiated among the MIR community over the years using text, audio, description, drawing, temporal envelope, sketches etc to bridge the so-called *semantic-gap* of MIR systems. These are further explained in Section 2.2.4

One of the early commercial systems developed in taking account of the content-based audio retrieval approaches with perceptual audio features were done by *Muscleftish*[7] (1996). Despite of this attempt, most of the current commercial sound management systems are not taking in account of the timbral attributes of sound which we believe can be highly beneficial in retrieving non-musical ambiguous sounds. Although this problem has been extensively studied in various MIR studies, so far of our knowledge, there hasn't been any noticeable attempt in integrating these high-level timbral features to commercial sound management systems using content-based audio retrieval techniques.

On the other hand, there are huge amount of creative commons licensed audio content in the web platforms such as *freesound*¹. Re-usability of these collaborative collections of audio content from platforms are being studied in the context of EU funded project Audio Commons², which aims to develop frameworks and tools in integrating creative commons licensed audio content into creative media industries such as in film, television and gaming industries. In respect to this initiative, *Pearce, A et all*, identified that perceptual timbral qualities such as brightness, hardness, depth etc were the most frequently searched semantic text terms by the users in *freesound* for retrieving sound samples [8]. By ambiguous sounds, we refer to non-musical sounds, foley sounds and sounds with no identifiable origin of source or sounds described by abstract concepts. Hence, all our future references to the term

¹<https://freesound.org>

²<https://audiocommons.org>

ambiguous sounds should be understood within this context.

Recently authors of [9] have proposed a structured hierarchical ontology³ named *AudioSet* of 632 audio classes guided by the literature and manual curation. This ontology made noticeable attempts in defining and structuring the ambiguous class sounds in a broad sense. We used a dataset of manually curated subset of sound classes from the above mentioned ontology in [9] and sounds from the *Freesound Dataset* [10] for the evaluation of our proposed system. More detailed methodology of dataset preparation can be found in Section 2.1.2.

1.1 Motivation

The main motivation behind this work is the absence of novel sound browsers in computer-assisted audio production environments which can ease the creative and technical work-flow of expert-users. By expert-users, we refer to professionals who used these environments to produce professional creative projects for an average of at least 10 years. This includes sound designers, foley artists, sound editors, musicians etc. When it comes to creating a multi-layer soundscape, sound designers heavily rely on commercial sound effects collections in addition to their own collections of recordings. Current sound browsers in Digital Audio Workstations (DAW) and Game-Audio Middlewares⁴ host a list-based auditioning approach where the user retrieves a list of relevant audio files by inputting a target query by specifying descriptions of text, tags, categories other meta-data. Then the user have to audition these list of audio files one by one in order to retrieve the desired sound. This is very time consuming and often stagnates the creative process of soundscape design, music production and other processes in audio production pipelines. This problem even more intensifies if the user is dealing with huge sound databases (eg. film, computer games) or unstructured collaborative sound collections (eg. freesound.org).

In the context of Music Information Retrieval (MIR) research, the problems of audio content retrieval and automatic sound classification systems have been investi-

³<https://research.google.com/audioset/ontology/index.html>

⁴https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_game_middleware

gated through various studies. Most of these approaches rely on the methodology of content-based audio retrieval, where a bag-of-features are extracted from the audio itself in order to classify and retrieve them [4], [2]. These extracted features represents various musical and non-musical facets of the sound.

Over the years, audio content retrieval has been moving in direction of computing audio similarity which is subjective and hard to compute objectively due to the complex nature of sound [4]. Despite the work done by *Musclefish*[7], there has been very less efforts in integrating content-based audio retrieval systems into general audio production environments. They analyzed sounds in terms of specific set of psychoacoustic features such as loudness, duration, pitch etc. Although there has been noticeable works done within MIR community in terms of content-based audio retrieval, especially in our use-case, most of the worked used multidimensional audio feature spaces using various dimensional directionality techniques to cluster similar sounds together and thus facilitating the retrieval process. However, these concepts were much abstract and have been abstain in integrating into various audio production pipelines due to lack of understanding the needs of user agents. A compilation of recent advances in content-based audio retrieval systems are detailed in section 2.2.2.

But even after a decade of advancements in MIR research, none of these approaches have been adapted into the current audio production environments. As a result of this, audio professionals and musicians are forced to use the above-mentioned less effective list-based auditioning approach while dealing with big unstructured sound databases.

Another key motivation for this work is the ongoing EU funded project Audio Commons⁵ which aims to bring creative commons licensed audio content into creative industries. We believe the proposed timbral attributes are useful in effective retrieval of non-musical abstract sounds, especially in dealing with a heterogeneous collection sounds as in freesound.org.

⁵<http://www.audiocommons.org>

We believe these questions should be addressed in bringing advancements of MIR researches in effective audio content management in creative industries.

The importance of user-centered MIR systems have been well emphasized and focused in the recent years within the MIR research community [11], [2]. Thus in the case of audio production environments, a well understanding of context, workflow, tools, pipelines are necessary in order to implement context-relevant sound description, classification and retrieval.

1.2 Objectives and Thesis Structure

The main objectives of this research is to asses the usability of perceptual timbral attributes (*brightness, hardness, roughness, depth*) proposed in [8] in browsing ambiguous sound effect libraries inside audio production environments. This study also aims to propose some possible paradigms to be considered while building user-centered audio retrieval systems for audio production environments using qualitative evaluation studies and interviews with expert-user agents. We believe that by understanding the challenges and problems in this audio production workflow from the expert-users themselves might help us to converge in practical solutions for the development of efficient sound management systems in future. In respect to *AudioCommons* initiative [12], this work also aims to aid and asses the research and technologies developed in the project to further integrate specific use cases such as in standard audio production pipeline.

This work is mainly structured in the following order. The context and the research problem are introduced in Chapter 1. Relevant literatures are reviewed in Chapter 2. Next, different components of our proposed system are further detailed. Observations and qualitative user-evaluations of the suggested system are detailed in Chapter 4. In the last chapter, we summarize and describe our work in terms of reproducibility and discuss future guidelines and improvements for further research in the field. A compiled version of expert-user agents evaluations were also proposed for driving further user-centric audio retrieval systems.

Chapter 2

State of the art

In this chapter, we discuss some key concepts and existing research works which have been relevant to our proposed system, from semantic sound descriptions, content-based audio retrieval systems and to the concepts of user interaction, design and usability in audio production environments.

2.1 Sound Descriptions

Proper description of sounds is the first step to effective retrieval of sound samples. It involves identifying acoustic, perceptual and semantic attributes of sound. Most of the initial efforts in understanding and describing sound have been done in psychoacoustical studies. Over the past two decades the developments in MIR¹ researches have also facilitated novel ways in understanding and describing sounds [2]. In this section, we further discuss about the key attributes of sound and the relevant methods which have been investigated to describe them. Since it is a broad area to discuss, we put a focus on studies which are more relevant to our proposed system.

¹Music Information Retrieval

2.1.1 Taxonomic Organization

The taxonomical organization of sound is the very first step in sound classification. The emergence of *musique concrète* paved the way for an extensive study in this area in the context of perceptual soundscapes and psychoacoustics. There have been mainly two important traditional approaches in taxonomic organization of sounds, one based on Schaeffer's morphology [13] and the other one on Gavers' ecological acoustics hypothesis [14]. Schaeffer in his prolific work *Traité des objets musicaux*, proposes that sounds can be characterized by their own intrinsic properties rather than by their source of generation [13], [15]. From psychoacoustical point of view, these properties are identified as the perceptual and acoustic attributes of sound, such as loudness, timbre, pitch etc. A detailed explanation of these attributes are further discussed in section 2.1.3.

An overview of Schaeffer's morphology can be seen in fig. 1 (taken from [16]). The matter criteria represents spectral distribution of the sounds, shape criteria describes the temporal characteristics such as dynamics and amplitude envelopes and the variation criteria describes changes in both matter and shape.

<i>MATTER CRITERIA</i>		
MASS Perception of "noisiness"	HARMONIC TIMBRE Bright/Dull	GRAIN Microstructure of the sound
<i>SHAPE CRITERIA</i>		
DYNAMICS Intensity evolution	ALLURE Amplitude or Fre- quency Modulation	
<i>VARIATION CRITERIA</i>		
MELODIC PRO- FILE: pitch varia- tion type	MASS PROFILE Mass variation type	

Figure 1: Schaeffer's typo-morphology as in [16].

There have been several attempts on sound descriptions following Schaeffer's work on sound objects as in [15]. Perhaps, one of the first approaches catered to audio production scenario was mentioned as in [17], the authors proposed some sound

description schema and ontology management of environmental sounds using various morphological descriptions based on sound objects. Later author The most common approach in these previous works were the description and classification of sounds in terms of its temporal envelope properties such as *stable*, *impulsive*, *stable*, *increasing*, *decreasing*, *increasing-decreasing* etc as in [18] and [19] etc.

Figure 2: Gavers' taxonomical organization of sounds as in [20].

On the other hand, Gaver proposed a taxonomy based on different type of materials and possible interactions between them [14] (based on how or from where the sound is produced). He introduced the taxonomy on the assertion that sounds are produced by the interaction of materials. As shown in Figure 2, Gavers' taxonomy is found to be particularly useful in describing and classifying environmental sounds [20], [21]. However, the art of foley recording (imitating and recording sounds for specific visual cues) reminds us that two physically different events with different objects can produce perceptually similar sounds, such as squeezing a box of cornstarch to imitate footsteps in the snow. The sound effects were sometimes judged as more realistic than recordings of the target events, also dealing with abstract sounds (sounds which does not have identifiable source, such as glitches, hits, pop sounds), Gavers' taxonomy failed to provide a useful description. Taking account of its potential in environmental sound description, different studies have been conducted on auditory scene detection and classification of environmental and urban sound collections as described in [20] and [21].

Since our study is focused on an heterogeneous collection of ambiguous sound effect samples as mentioned in section 1.1.1, we are interested in an hybrid approach to define our taxonomy of sound effects dataset. However, Google's recently released

AudioSet² ontology[9] proposed more broad and extensive sound taxonomy based on ontologies. They were created using carefully structured hierarchical ontology of 635 audio classes guided by the literature and manual curation. Figure 3, shows the screenshot of an interactive tree visualization of the audio ontology by Jordi Pons.

Figure 3: Tree visualization³of AudioSet Ontology[9]

AudioSet dataset was build using human labelers to annotate the presence of specific audio classes in 10 second segments of YouTube⁴videos. Due to inconvenience of extracting audio from the YouTube videos for our experiment, we decided to use *Freesound Dataset* (FSD) [10] which maps sound from freesoung.org to AudioSet ontology. FSD has a collaborative platform where annotation and validations are crowd-sourced from various expert users. More details of the FSD can be found in

²<https://research.google.com/audioset/ontology/index.html>

³<http://www.jordipons.me/apps/audioset>

⁴<https://www.youtube.com>

[10] and further details and methodology of our dataset preparation for the task can be found in section 3.1.1 and 3.1.2.

2.1.2 Perceptual Sound Attributes

Perceptual sound attributes are intrinsic qualities of sounds that are depended on the subjective perceptual auditory sensation of human auditory system. Perceptual sensations caused by these sound attributes were extensively studied in the field of psychoacoustics. These attributes have been studied by various authors in the realm of subjective duration, loudness, dynamics, pitch, timbre and spatial properties of sound. A compilation of these studies and standards can be found in [5], [22] and [1]. It is also important to notice that the the musical aspects of some these facets like timbre has not been covered in this section since it's not in the scope of this project. Hence in the following sections we explain loudness, dynamics and timbre in the scope of this project.

Loudness and Dynamics

Loudness is generally described as the subjective impression of the intensity of sound. Loudness is highly related with the frequency content, temporal evolution and duration of the signal. American National Standards Institute (ANSI) describes loudness as that attribute of auditory sensation in terms of which sounds can be ordered on a scale extending from quiet to loud [23]. However, there has been studies and observations which portrays the inadequacies of this ANSI definitions [1]. To measure loudness, the volume of a 1khz reference tone is adjusted until it is perceived by listeners to be equally as loud as the sound being measured (in *phons*).

Dynamics refers to the effective perception of variation of loudness. Musicologists explains this sensations in terms such as *crescendo*, *decrescendo* etc. These knowledge has been exploited in certain studies of morphological sound description as seen in [18], [24] and [19]. Recently, authors of [25] proposed loudness profiles using morphological sound description mentioned above and thus again confirming the usefulness of these descriptors.

Dynamics is also highly related with temporal envelope of a sound. Envelope represents how the sound evolves over time. In sound and music it has well understood by the users in terms of *attack, decay, sustain, release* (ADSR) envelopes. In [26], [27], the authors proposed using these attributes for retrieving and filtering sounds in visual interfaces like drawing the approximate envelope shape itself.

Timbre

Timbre is the most difficult and poorly defined attribute of sound. In [28], Bregman pointed out timbre as "everything that is not loudness, pitch or spatial perception". Despite of being an abstract concept, perhaps, this would be the best description that we can give for timbre. ANSI⁵ describes timbre as "that attribute of auditory sensation in terms of which a listener can judge two sounds, similarly presented and having the same pitch and loudness, are different".

Figure 4: Timbre space as proposed in [29]

Psychoacoustic studies point out that timbre doesn't have a physical counterpart unlike there perceptual features. It's multidimensionality nature makes objective measurements very difficult [29]. In [29] *McAdams et al* proposed the timbre space to project audio into multidimensional space using audio features to distinguish the

⁵American National Standards Institute

timbre of various musical instruments. Figure 4 shows the timbre space proposed in [29].

From a MIR perspective, timbre has been extensively studied through out the years. Even though is not well defined, MIR community studies timbre by extracting various temporal, spectral and spatial features of audio itself. One of the first approach in compiling large set of audio features (which corresponds perceptual acoustic features) were done in [6]. Later attempts were done in building collective algorithms for extracting audio features correlates to timbre sensation[30].

As we are dealing with ambiguous sound collections, perhaps the most effective way in describing these sounds would be using timbral descriptions (describing how particular the sound sounds in terms of acoustical or semantic-textual features). Hence systems based on semantic description mapped timbral characteristics shows a potential in dealing with these kind of sound collections. Since we are only focusing on the the timbral attributes of non-musical sounds, the musical aspect of timbre (correlation with the pitch and tonal attributes) was not taken in account in our studies. Relevant previous attempts in describing semantic timbral attributes are further mentioned in the next section.

2.1.3 Semantic Descriptions

Generally, semantic descriptions helps to model a range of ideas that are more technical into something which is more understandable and relating to end users⁶ in various discipline across science. In traditional information retrieval approaches these semantics is conveyed using textual descriptions (corresponds to how users describe and search sounds). In the case of audio retrieval, most of the commercial systems rely on audio meta-data, curated textual descriptions and tags to allow users to search the database more semantically.

In respect to semantic descriptions of sound there have been efforts in psychoacoustical and MIR studies. In the content-based audio retrieval studies, there have

⁶Chambers Biographical Dictionary, 5e.1990, p.202

been comparatively less efforts in semantic description. However in the recent years there have been high interest on this topic from the MIR and audio researchers community. In content-based audio retrieval, the search process works by taking the extracted audio features as search parameter for the query. These features often doesn't correlates with how humans describe sound. For example, describing a sound is *bright* is more understandable than saying the sound has high *spectral centroid mean*. Conceptually, this is one of the classic problem in the MIR researches often called as *semantic-gap*. Building high-level audio features that constitutes with how users define sound might reduce this so called *semantic-gap*. One of the easy way of describing sound semantically (besides its source) is on its perceptual acoustical qualities which is correlated to timbre [31]. On the same time, it is very hard to provide objective semantic description to sound based on these descriptions due to the complex psychoacoustical nature of sound.

One of the early notable standardization approach in audio content management was from MPEG-7 framework [17]. The MPEG-7 standard provides description mechanisms and ontology management tools for multimedia documents [25]. Following this framework with Schaeffer's typo-morphology, Cano, P. et al [17] proposed an automatic sound classification system. Later authors of [32] also proposed an automatic sound classification system based on semantic morphological description of sound. There has been some efforts in integrating textual semantic networks such as wordnet⁷ for building sound taxonomies with a focus on audio production environments as in [24].

Regarding semantic timbral description, there have been noticeable research in the field of acoustics and sound quality description. Most of these studies made efforts in semantic description in terms of various elements in sound features, microphone/loudspeaker systems, quality, spatial etc. There have been recent attempts defining semantic features in audio production environments through crowdsourcing annotations and ratings [34]. As a part of AudioCommons⁸ initiative, Pierce, A et al [33] made a compilation of all the state of the art works done in semantic timbral

⁷<https://wordnet.princeton.edu/>

⁸<http://www.audiocommons.org/>

Source	Number of attributes	Topic
Bagousse et al. [2010]	28	Spatial/Timbral
Cano [2006]	10	Sound description
Choisel [2007]	8	Multichannel reproduction
Davies et al. [2013]	49	Environmental/Soundscape
Disley et al. [2006]	17	Musical instrument
Gabrielsson et al. [1979]	13	Loudspeakers
Handel [1995]	16	Timbre
Hermes [2014]	105	Mix quality
Jensen [N.D.]	8	Timbre
Koivuniemi and Zacharov [2001]	12	Spatial sound
Levandier et al. [2008]	3	Loudspeakers
Lokki et al. [2011]	10	Concert halls
Lorho [2005]	16	Headphones
Mattila [2001a, 2001b, 2002, 2003] (Summarised in Bech and Zacharov [2006])	27	Speech
Michaud et al. [2015]	4	Loudspeakers
Pearce et al. [2016]	40	Microphones
Pedersen [2008]	647	Reproduced sound
Pedersen [2015]	42	Reproduced sound
Staffeldt [1974]	38	Loudspeakers
Wrzeciono and Marasek [2010]	11	Musical instrument
Zacharov and Pedersen [2015]	34	Reproduced sound
Zwicker and Fastl [2007]	2	Timbre perception

Figure 5: A compilation of semantic perceptual sound attributes from the literature as in [33].

feature descriptions of non-musical sounds. Figure 5, Table containing state-of-the-art studies in semantic audio description. In order to identify the relevance of these semantic timbral attributes in users' point of view, they did a study which gather the

Figure 6: Histogram showing most frequently searched semantic timbral terms by the users in freesound as in [33].

frequency of textual search of timbral attributes by the users in Freesound⁹. From the results of these studies, a relevant list of most sought after relevant timbral attributes were identified. Figure 6, shows a weighted histogram of different timbral attributes and their frequency-of-search by the users in freesound.org platform.

Authors of [33] identified six high-level timbral features after an internal iteration of quality assessment. The identified semantic timbral qualities are *brightness*, *depth*, *hardness*, *roughness*. A collection of light-weight timbral model algorithms were developed as in [8] in context of AudioCommons EU project[12]. These frameworks for sound description aims to achieve better audio retrieval of sound samples in big databases. We believe especially in the case of ambiguous sounds and collaborative sound collections, these high-level features have the potential to improve the audio retrieval and thus help the audio professionals. We further discuss more detail about these concepts below.

⁹<http://www.freesound.org/>

2.2 Content-Based Audio Retrieval Systems

In this section, we discuss about various content-based audio retrieval systems proposed in the literature. Specially, we investigate various methodologies proposed for the search and visualization process for browsing non-musical sounds inside audio production environments.

2.2.1 Search Design Concepts

Search process can be seen from two angles. One is the process of properly describing what you want to search and other is to develop smart technologies to translate and understand your description and then retrieve relevant results according to it. These problems were extensively studied on various realms during the advancements of MIR studies. Content-based retrieval are usually done by computing specific audio feature vectors (audio features corresponds to both acoustic and perceptual qualities computed from the audio) and then matched against the possible similarity with other feature vectors of files in the database. Muscle Fish proposed one of the initial approach to content-based audio retrieval of generic sound databases [7].

Over the years, the development of content-based audio retrieval studies paved the emergence of different query techniques such as in *speech recognition systems*, *query by word*, *query by humming*, *query sketching*, *query by example* etc [2]. Certain techniques such as *dynamic querying* from traditional IR studies [35] were also found to useful in audio retrieval systems [27].

On the other side, some recent research studies also propose the possibility of searching sounds by allowing users to graphically sketch the mental representations of sound [36].

2.2.2 Visualization Concepts

Advancements in information retrieval studies shows that visual data exploration has found to be useful when little is known about the data and the goals of exploration

are vague [37]. In literature, most of the visualization concepts in content-based retrieval are based on extracting certain audio feature descriptors from audio and project it to a multidimensional feature space using dimensionality reduction techniques such as Principle Component Analysis (PCA), Self Organizing Maps (SOM), t-distributed Stochastic Neighbour Embedding (t-SNE) etc as in [27], [38], [26], [39]. These visualization concepts were also explored in the concatenative synthesis studies and audio-mosaicing [40], [41]. Figure 7, shows some examples of visualization approaches in the literature.

Figure 7: Screenshots of several visualization approaches in content-based audio retrieval as in [39] [27], [26], [38]

Recent studies proposes that multidimensional space are seems to be useful when the user want to explore and create new stuffs, especially explore the creative process of music production and performance itself [41]. However, this has been not been extensively studied in the case of audio post-production.

2.3 Concepts of User Interaction and Usability

The user plays a key role for all MIR applications. Authors of [2], [11] and [3] specifically emphasizes the importance of understanding the user needs, behavior and contexts when developing MIR systems. In the case of content-based retrieval,

most of the systems were designed as a way to evaluate different algorithms. In recent years there have been some efforts in bridging these gap by specific user-centric studies. We discuss some of these examples in the next sections

2.3.1 User Interaction in MIR Systems

In [3], the authors mentions that the MIR field has been more focused on developing systems and algorithms than on understanding user needs and behavior. As a recent general shift in all the disciplines of ICT research, the MIR community has been also shift away from system centric design to user-centric ones. Some innovative approach in concerning with audio production environments were the works done in in done using audio mosaicing and concatenative synthesis [40] and [41]. But these approaches were particularly focused and found to mostly beneficial in a music production scenario [41]. However, there have been arguments claiming that digital audio workstations have not been keeping up with the rapid changes in common computing paradigms and modern digital audio workstation softwares are largely mimic analogue devices both functionally and visually.

2.3.2 Existing Systems in Audio Production Environments

Figure 8: Screenshots of sound browsers in Avid Pro Tools and Apple Logic Pro (see appendix).

The audio production workflow in creative industries varies according to different use

cases. Perhaps, one of the main difference is on non-interactive (linear) and interactive audio production workflow. As we moved to computer assisted production, recording and storage facilities, audio professionals have been heavily rely on Digital Audio Workstations for all sorts of audio processing, storage and retrieval. This pose the importance of audio retrieval systems in production pipelines. Since then, various systems has been developed both inside and outside DAW's to manage sound collections. However, still these systems are rely on the text meta-data of the audio file. Figure 8 shows the screenshot of sound browsers of DAWs Avid Protools¹⁰ and Apple Logic Pro¹¹.

Figure 9: Screenshots of some advance commercial sound management systems available in the market. SoundMiner¹⁵, AudioFinder¹⁶, Netmix¹⁷

Figure 9, show some of the advance dedicated commercial sound browsers. They have cross-platform support, cloud storage and easy integration, processing and management of local databases. Even though there are some more products in the market, these products were chosen as suggested by expert-users as industry standard products.

¹⁰<http://www.avid.com/pro-tools>

¹¹<https://www.apple.com/lae/logic-pro/>

2.4 Summary

We have provided a general overview of most relevant state of the art studies to our proposed system. A review of modern psychoacoustic literature reveals the definitions of ANSI are not particularly useful, since these definitions doesn't provide a clear distinction between attribute such as loudness, pitch and timbre. In [1], Houtsma mentioned it's mainly because these definitions are almost depended on the semantic difference between the endpoints of scales soft-loud vs low-high. It is interesting that in the case of content-based audio retrieval, we believe that using high-level timbral attributes with relative scales would be useful since there are no objective definitions and still users are able to filter the search results based on a relative subjective scale which is be relevant in the audio production domain. In the case of browsing big sound databases this can be highly beneficial. On the same time, it has been visible in the literature that there have been very less efforts in understanding the needs of expert-users in audio production industry from the MIR community. So our main focus would be develop a probe system using existing high-level perceptual timbral attributes and evaluate, understand the users needs and further outline new directions in the development.

Chapter 3

System Development

In this chapter we explain the concepts and implementation of our proposed system. The system was developed in an experimental setup to further conduct expert-user studies. A general overview of the tools and materials employed for the development of the proposed prototype is further explained in the next sections.

3.1 Methodology

Our main aim of developing this system was to study the usability of perceptual timbral attributes in the audio retrieval process. This studies also points out the underlying problems in the search process itself. Our main methodology was to develop a probe system to observe it's in a real context (audio production), then evaluate it and further inspire new ideas for research.

3.2 System Framework

During our research we identified different software frameworks which were suited for the implementation. As discussed in section 2.5, DAWs (Digital Audio Workstations) use certain standard frameworks and interfaces (VST, AU etc) for integrating external systems (plug-ins). Software development in these frameworks demand quite certain amount of resource, effort and time (which was not accessible) and in

our case we just want a proof-of-concept system. Hence, Cycling74s' Max¹ visual programming language was chosen in considering easy prototyping, feasibility and it's easy integration into audio production environments. Mostly, it's compatibility with Ableton Live² DAW as Max for Live device (M4L)³ was ideal for us to present our prototypes to the expert users inside a environment which is familiar to them. Moreover, Max facilitate easy prototyping and support of embedding Javascript⁴ programming language, which was crucial in implementing efficient *client-server* communication. The system generally follows a *client-server* scheme where Max software acts as a client application to accessing freesound API⁵ services and local JSON files (refer to section for more about feature extraction process). Figure 9 shows the general block diagram of the distance.

Figure 10: Block diagram of the proposed system

There were mainly 4 important phases in the development project such as dataset preparation, timbral feature extraction, query and interface design. These are further explained in the next sections.

¹<https://cycling74.com/products/max>

²<https://www.ableton.com/en/live/>

³<https://www.ableton.com/en/live/max-for-live/>

⁴<https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/JavaScript>

⁵<http://freesound.org/apiv2/>

3.2.1 Dataset

Considering research reproducibility and our motivation from AudioCommons⁶ initiative, we decided to use the sounds from Freesound⁷. We created two datasets named as *FS-AMB-SFX* and *FS-AMB-SFX-700* respectively. At the end we only used the FS-AMB-SFX-700 dataset for our studies. The dataset preparation processes are further explained in the next sections.

FS-AMB-SFX dataset

As mentioned in section 1.2, we used the recently released freesound dataset[10] which maps sounds from freesound.org to google’s audioset ontology[9]. Later, we compiled a set of 80 potential sound categories of ambiguous sounds. By ambiguous sounds we are referring to non-musical sounds, foley sounds and sounds with no identifiable origin or abstract concepts. We compiled sounds into our proposed dataset : FS-AMB-SFX dataset.

FS-AMB-SFX-700 dataset

Freesound dataset (FSD)[10] has crowd-sourced user annotation and validation. Only having around 6% (at the time of writing this document) of manually annotated and validated sounds in the entire FSD[10], there weren’t enough number of sounds in some categories inside the FS-AMB-SFX dataset.

Figure 11: FS-AMB-SFX-700 dataset, 100 sounds each in 7 sound classes.

Hence, 7 sound classes were chose from the FS-AMB-SFX dataset and compiled it into a new shorter version dataset as FS-AMB-SFX-700 dataset. Figure 9., shows the structure of the proposed dataset. Additional sounds were download using some

⁶<http://www.audiocommons.org>

⁷<http://freesound.org>

custom scripts which are available in my public github repository⁸, later these sounds were manually annotated and validated to form the final dataset.

Also, since we didn't want to complex the task of user evaluation and specifically want to focus on the problem of retrieval with perceptual features rather audio classification itself, the methodology behind choosing the sound categories were purely biased on the subjective quality, availability, frequency of use, usefulness of sounds.

3.2.2 Feature Extraction

We used the timbral sound models developed by Pierce, A et al [8] in context of EU funded project AudioCommons[12]. Since the feature extraction process is not feasible to run on real-time, we decided to do a off-line (local) feature extraction.

Selected features

Among 6 timbral feature models developed as in [8], 4 of the following features were chosen. The other two features (Metallic and Reverb) were omitted since we believe these models will bring more ambiguity in the search process.

- * Timbral Depth [8]
- * Timbral Roughness[8]
- * Timbral Hardness[8]
- * Timbral Brightness[8]

A detailed explanation of the development of the above features are outlined in [8]. Besides that, some meta-data of sounds such as unique identifier, filename and license attribution were also parsed from freesound.org in further visualizing search results.

⁸<https://github.com/albincorreya/smcmasterthesis2017>

Batch feature extraction

As mentioned in section 3.1.1, we only used FS-AMB-SFX-700 dataset for the implemented prototype. A batch feature extraction script⁹ were developed in Python¹⁰ programming language as the timbral models were also implemented in python. Feature extraction were done locally for all the sounds in the FS-AMB-SFX-700 dataset.

```
for sound in files:
    if not count>100:
        if not sound.endswith('.mp3') or sound.endswith('.ogg'):
            print '\n-----'+str(i)+'-----'
            str_sound = sound.split('_')
            #print '\nSPLIT',str_sound
            sound_id = str_sound[0]
            sound_name = str_sound[1]
            print '\n\tComputing feature for sound >>',sound
            fname = path + folder + '/' + sound
            try:
                brightness = bright.timbral_brightness(fname)
                print '\t.....brightness done'
                roughness = rough.timbral_roughness(fname)
                print '\t.....roughness done'
                hardness = hard.timbral_hardness(fname)
                print '\t.....hard done'
                depthness = depth.timbral_depth(fname)
                print '\t.....depth done'
```

Figure 12: A code snippet from the batch extraction script

This batch extraction script outputs a JSON file for each of the sound class with all the selected timbral features, freesound sound identifier and filename corresponding to each sound. JSON file format were selected in considering the easy integration and processing of dictionary objects in Max language. JSON files were structured as shown in figure 13 for every sound class.

These files are stored into the local disk for further processing in the system.

⁹https://github.com/albincorreya/smcmasterthesis2017/blob/master/multiclass_timbralfeature_extractor.py

¹⁰<https://www.python.org/>

```

"32575": {
  "sound_name": "Carpet footsteps.wav.wav",
  "depth": 30.224844607533527,
  "roughness": 0.016836276511400506,
  "hardness": 44.293247582894764,
  "brightness": 40.7057413973351
},
"243794": {
  "sound_name": "Footsteps of soldier on ground.wav.wav",
  "depth": 32.79201636891792,
  "roughness": 0.40552007911005405,
  "hardness": 76.79123037158115,
  "brightness": 67.82320847572781
},

```

Figure 13: JSON file structure of computed timbral feature values for each sounds

3.2.3 Client-side

Freesound Max-MSP Modules

Freesound Max/MSP modules¹¹ is a client-side library for interacting with freesound API¹² services inside Max-MSP environment. These reusable Max patches encapsulates different search functionalities of freesound API [42] and thus allowing audio professionals to use freesound service directly inside audio production environments. For the moment, the library only supports some of the basic resources from freesound-API which was essential for our research. More features will be added soon in the development process. The library was designed on a modular approach inspired from the modular synthesizers¹³ (which is familiar to audio professionals) where you can connect different modules with input and output cables. As Max-MSP a visual programming language, we believe this approach is intuitive for the users. This library was build by optimizing Stefan Brunners' elevator generator project¹⁴.

- ***fs.oauth2*** Freesound implements OAuth2 authorization work-flow in order to access some of their API resources such as downloading original sounds and uploading etc. The OAuth 2.0 is a authorization framework that enables a third-party application to obtain limited access to an HTTP service. It allows

¹¹<https://github.com/albincorreya/Freesound-Max-MSP-Modules>

¹²<http://freesound.org/apiv2/>

¹³https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Modular_synthesizer

¹⁴<http://stb.klingt.org/ElevatorMusicGenerator/>

specific authorization flows for web applications, desktop applications, mobile phones, and living room devices. This specification is being developed within the IETF OAuth WG¹⁵.

Figure 14: Interface of *fs.oauth2* module

fs.oauth2 module implemented OAuth2 authorization of freesound API in Max-MSP. This module make freesound.org resources more accessible to people who are not familiar to web development frameworks. Hence the user-friendly approach of *fs.oauth2* module interface aims to help audio-visual artists, audio researchers and professionals to easily access freesound.org resources without worrying much about web frameworks and its implementation. Thus it's a key part of our proposed system. Figure 13, show an screen-shot of the module itself. It uses *jweb*¹⁶ max object to embed web browser inside the interface. The module has the following input/output specifications.

Inputs : A json file the a specific API user credentials.

Outputs :

access_token : After authorizing with user login in the browser interface, the max app will be able to obtain an access token which provides temporary, secure access to Freesound API.

client_id : Client id of your freesound API credential parsed from the json file.

¹⁵<https://www.ietf.org/>

¹⁶<https://docs.cycling74.com/max5/refpages/max-ref/jweb.html>

client_secret (*api_key*) : Client secret or API key of your freesound API credential parsed from the json file.

- ***fs.search_standard*** This module encapsulate some of the basic text search resources as specified in the freesound-API documentation¹⁷. It is designed to use along with *fs.oauth2* module. Figure 14, shows the interface of *fs.search_standard* along with *fs.preview* module.

Figure 15: Interface of *fs.search_standard* along with *fs.preview* module

For the moment, users can specify four basic search parameters such as *text query*, *filter by tags*, *page_size*, and *audio format* as provided in the API search resources[42]. This module under further development and in future most of different parameters would be added accordingly.

Inputs :

client_secret or *api_key* : API key obtained from the *fs.oauth2* module.

access_token : access token obtained from the *fs.oauth2* module.

Outputs :

sound_id : freesound sound identifier corresponding to your selection of sound cell on the interface.

- ***fs.preview*** - This module is used to retrieve freesound low-quality audio preview from the server by specifying the sound identifier. The module plays the audio preview on the default audio device on the system whenever an sound identifier

¹⁷http://freesound.org/docs/api/resources_apiv2.html#search-resources

has been received by the module. This had achieved by using *jweb* max object. This module is designed work with *fs.search_standard* module.

Inputs :

access_token -

bang - outputs - Audio preview on default audio device of the system

- ***fs.download*** - This module allows the user to download a sound in its original format/quality (the format/quality with which the sound was uploaded) to the local disk of the user. It requires OAuth2 authentication, hence it's designed to use along with *fs.oauth2* module.

Figure 16: Interface of *fs.download* module

Inputs :

sound_id - Freesound sound identifier

access_token - outputs :

fs.download uses *buffer*¹⁸ object in max to load the downloaded sound for audio preview. Sounds loaded in *buffer* object are easily accessible in Max environment by just referring it's variable name and thus allowing the users to various kind of audio signal processing to create interesting soundscapes.

- ***fs.player (Sampler)*** *fs.player* is an basic audio sampler device which has been built in combining various freesound max msp modules. It has various simple audio processing capabilities such as looping, pitch shifting, time-stretching etc. It depicts the example use-cases of the proposed *Freesound Max-MSP*

¹⁸<https://docs.cycling74.com/max5/refpages/msp-ref/buffer.html>

modules. Beside all other modules, *fs.player* module can be also used as an *Max for Live (M4L)* device inside *Ableton Live* DAW. This device has been developed in order showcase capabilities of above explained *freesound max-msp modules*.

Figure 17: Interface of *fs.player* module

Embedded JavaScripts

The main part of the *freesound max-msp client-library* (also our proposed system) has been implemented using embedded JavaScript functions in *Max-Msp* which facilitated us in handling HTTP requests and JSON file parsing efficiently. *Max-MSP* provides native support of JavaScript programming language using *max JS*¹⁹ objects. In JavaScript, this can be achieved through *ajax request*²⁰. All API services used in *freesound max-msp modules* like *oauth2 authorization*, *audio preview*, *audio download*, *search resources* were implemented using embedded JavaScript. We used the standard *XMLHttpRequest*²¹ object in JavaScript to achieve this. Since explaining each process inside the JavaScript functions is out of the scope of our project we are not further explaining it here. You can find documented script in my public repository mentioned in Appendix - A.

```

1 function searchSounds()
2 {
3   xmlhttp = new XMLHttpRequest();
4   xmlhttp.open("GET", url);
5   xmlhttp.setRequestHeader("Authorization", "Bearer " + access_token);
6   xmlhttp.onreadystatechange = readystatechange_parsejson;

```

¹⁹<https://docs.cycling74.com/max5/refpages/max-ref/js.html>

²⁰<https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/AJAX>

²¹<https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/API/XMLHttpRequest>

```
7  xmlhttp.send();  
8 }
```

The above code block demonstrates the implementation of ajax request for accessing freesound-api search resources.

Besides web services, an embedded JavaScript 'jsonparsor.js' has been used in the proposed system to implement the dynamic search/ranking functions by parsing an input JSON file. On top of that, these JavaScript functions can be easily reused in building similar systems in web development frameworks using HTML and CSS.

3.3 Implementation

In this section, we explain how the proposed system was implemented in terms of search query and its interface design.

3.3.1 Query Design

As mentioned in the above section, a default set of sounds are loaded whenever an user selects an sound class using the sound class UI button in the interface. Here explain the query mechanisms we implemented in the proposed system.

JSON import

We import the fs-amb-sfx-700 dataset structured using the methods in section 3.2.2 into Max-MSP environment using native JavaScript *Dict*²² object in Max.

A code is snippet is attached below :

```
1  var sound_dict = new Dict;  
2  sound_dict.import_json(path);  
3  var class = main_dict.getkeys();
```

²²<https://docs.cycling74.com/max7/vignettes/jsdict>

Mode of queries

There are basically two methods of search functions that can be used for four different search modes.

- **Threshold-based filtering** In this approach, we set a threshold value and search is initiated for all the files with feature values within an upper and lower bound of the targeted input.
 - * *singleFilter()* - In this mode filtering is done based on one timbral attribute slider input whenever the user slides the particular slider.
 - * *multiFilter()* In this mode, filtering is done based on all the four timbral attribute sliders input. Whenever the user slides the particular slider, the *multiFilter()* function calls with the updated values.
- **Distance-based ranked sorting** In this approach, a simple euclidean distance will be calculated from the target input to all sounds in the json. Later the results will be sorted ascendingly according to the least distance value. In this way the sounds with closest value to the target will be top on the list while sounds which are far from the target value would be on the bottom.
 - * *singleRanker()* In this mode, ranking is only done with one slider input value.
 - * *multiRanker()* In this mode addition to *singleRanker()* function, users have a choice to select the attribute corresponding to the input slider value.

Features

Here we detail the extra features we deployed on the system.

- **Shuffle sound order on sound class loading** This feature is common in commercial advanced sound management systems to facilitate user to find different sound from the list order. This was implemented using the `Array.sort()` in-built function of JavaScript.

A code snippet below :

```

1 var sortedSounds = sounds.sort(function(a, b){return 0.5 - Math.
  random()}); //shuffles the order of elements in the array
  randomly

```

- **Dynamic query and feedback** : As inspired from modern IR systems and successful applications in MIR systems [35], our system was designed to give achieve near-real-time dynamic search and feedback as results.

This was mostly implemented in Max-MSP native objects, particularly using *pak* object²³

- **Descending sorting by specific attributes** This objective of this feature is to re-order the results given by the output of *multiFilter* search functions according to user selected timbral attributes. This is implemented using the `Array.sort()` built-in function in JavaScript.

A code snippet below :

```

1 var sortedSounds = sounds.sort(function(a, b){
2   var x=a[attr];var y=b[attr];return y - x}
3   );

```

3.3.2 Interface

As our intention was to build a probe system with perceptual attribute filtering, we decided to implement an simple interface which is similar to the design of traditional list-based sound browsers. Each individual parts of the user interface are further explained in the next steps. These UI objects dynamically interacts with the search functions and display results in order to give near real-time interaction. Figure 17, shows a screenshot of the proposed interface.

UI Objects

- **Authorize** Open *fs.oauth2* module for authorizing freesound API services

²³<https://docs.cycling74.com/max7/maxobject/pak>

Figure 18: Screenshot of user interface of the demo prototype

- **Sound Class Buttons** Loads meta-data sounds from the chosen class from sounds by the user.

Figure 19: Sound class UI Buttons

- **jit.cellblock object** Max-Msp table-styled object to display search results. Every clicks on the sound id cells automatically retrieves freesound low-quality audio preview on your default audio device.

Perceptual Search Module

This module encapsulates the dynamic UI functions to interact with the JavaScript search functions.

- **Attribute sliders** Slider objects to input target query values of respective timbral attributes to the module output.

Figure 20: Perceptual attribute sliders

- **Filter threshold knob** Knob object to input the threshold value *singleFilter* and *multiFilter* search modes.

Figure 21: Filter threshold knob

- **Search mode drop-down menu** drop-down menu object to choose the required search mode of retrieval.

Figure 22: Search mode drop-down menu

Figure 23: Sort by attributes drop-down menu

- ***Sort by attributes drop-down menu*** Drop-down menu to choose sorting methods of results based on a particular timbral attribute. This function is only applicable to *multiFilter* and *multiRanker* search modes.

Chapter 4

Evaluations and Discussions

In this chapter we further explain the steps taken in the evaluation and analysis processes and later summarized our findings.

4.1 Qualitative expert-user evaluation

As detailed in Section 2.2.3, user-centered approach tend to be an essential element in building useful MIR systems. Perhaps, this might be the main reason for the lack of integration of MIR researches into commercial sound management systems. We had conducted in-depth interviews and user evaluation sessions with expert-users in order to understand the problems of audio retrieval using timbral features. Then we further evaluate the developed prototype as explained in the next sections.

4.1.1 Goals of Evaluation

We specially focused on the following goals during the evaluation process.

- * Expert-user feedbacks of the proposed system.
- * Understanding the problems in sound retrieval with timbral attributes from a user point-of-view.
- * Gather feedbacks and suggest improvements to the perceptual timbral models.
- * Suggest improvements to the developed prototype.

- * Compiling innovative ideas from expert-users.
- * Outlining further guidelines for future research and development in the domain.

4.1.2 Participants

By expert-users we were focusing on individuals having nearly or more than 10 years of experience in audio productions work-flows. We had approached 8 expert-users from the audio industry for the evaluation. Their profile includes audio engineers, sound designers (Films/TV/games), music producers, product specialists, producers and audio researchers from the best research groups/companies/studios such as Avid, Abbey Road, Jukedek, MTG etc. These interview sessions were conducted before and after the prototype testing sessions.

4.1.3 Implementation

In this section, we further describes how we implemented the user study. Figure 24 shows the conceptual diagram of the process and its goals.

Figure 24: Methodology of the user evaluation process

The overall process was divided into 4 steps, pre-test questionnaire, prototype testing, post-test questionnaire and in-depth interview sessions. These are further ex-

plained in the next sections.

Test setup

In August 2017, we conducted several user tests and interviews with a total of 10 expert users as explained in section 4.1.2. A compiled package of software with readme files and respective online resources were delivered to the participants for setting up the system. The evaluation tests were conducted both locally and remotely according to the participants availability. A general context of this research was briefly explained to the participants before presenting the below mentioned tasks.

Pre-test questionnaire

A pre-test questionnaire was conducted with the selected participants in order to collect some demographic and contextual information regarding audio production workflows. A set of curated questions were framed to align the results to an general theme. Some of them are listed below.

Which description suits best for you ? *

- Mix Engineer
- Sound Designer (Film/TV)
- Foley Artist
- Recording Engineer
- Game Sound Designer
- Sound FX Editor
- Producer
- Audio Researcher
- Musician
- Film Maker/ Video Editor
- Other: _____

Figure 25: A screenshot from the pre-test questionnaire

- Years of experience ?
- Area of expertise ?
- Frequency of use of sound libraries?

- Most common source of these sound collections?
- Are you satisfied with the current sound browsers in the market ?
- If so, what is your favorite sound management tools in the market and why ?
- What is the most frustrating thing you had encounter in the search process ?
- How would be your dream sound management system be like ?

At this stage, several interview sessions were also conducted with selected users.

Prototype testing

In this step, we introduced the prototype system for further testing. All the required files and instructions were compiled to an single public repository¹ and made available to the expert-users. The testing session were conducted in various locations in Barcelona and some remote locations in London, Dubai and Mumbai. Figure 26 shows an image of a prototype testing at Caballo Grande Studios, Barcelona.

Figure 26: Image of a prototype testing session at Caballe Grande Studios, Barcelona

Since some our testing sessions were done remotely, a demo video² showcasing the basic functions of the system were also provided to all the candidates to give an basic idea of the system. The main idea was to observe and understand how the

¹<https://github.com/albincorreya/PerceptualSoundBrowser>

²<https://vimeo.com/231350962>

user will use the prototype and gather some interesting feedbacks for the analysis later.

Post-test questionnaire

Post-test questionnaire was aimed to collect some subjective feedback of the presented system. The questionnaire includes questions that demands reflections about system performance, user interaction and experience while using the proposed system. We followed a general theme of questions to the participants. Some of them are listed below.

Does the retrieved results by the system makes sense to you (perceptually relevant) ? Do you often get the sound you want while using these filters ? *

1 2 3 4 5

Not at all Almost all the time

Among the following, What features are relevant in an audio production scenario according to you ? *

Brightness

Depth

Hardness

Roughness

Figure 27: A screenshot from the post-test questionnaire

- Did the overall concept makes sense to you ?
- How much do you favor to see these timbral features in your sound management system or DAW?
- Did the retrieved results made sense (perceptually relevant) to you?
- Which timbral features you find useful in audio production scenario ?
- What feature would you like to see in your system ?
- What search mode options do you prefer in the interface ?
- What feature would you like to see in your system ?

- What improvements you would suggest ?

An interview sessions were conducted after this session with selected users. They are detailed in the next section.

4.1.4 In-depth interviews with expert-users

As mentioned before, in-depth interviews were conducted with available key icons from the audio industry. Altogether four participants from different realms of audio industry were chosen. The main aim was to further more understand the problem from a expert's perspective. At the very beginning of the conversations, an compilation of innovative research examples from the content-based retrieval systems studies were presented to the participants to give an general overview of advancements of both academic and industrial research. The participants were key figures and multi-skilled experts from the audio industries who has been closely involved in the creative and technological aspects audio production for over years. This session was aimed to extract more contextual information for their vast work experiences. The overall session was focused and structured on different aspects of audio production. These are further explained below.

- **Present challenges** At the very first phase of the session, participants were asked to share their experiences with various sound management systems over the years. A detailed discussion of various standards and conventions followed among big audio production houses were discussed. We also enquired about the difference of different workflow chains within audio production pipelines and their varied requirements. Several common problems and challenges of sound database management were discussed and important informations are compiled and outlined in section 4.2
- **Direct observations** One of our agenda in the in-depth interview sessions was to carefully observe the work-flow of expert-users within their personal production environments. The subjects were asked to demonstrate their regular

workflow of creating soundscapes with sound libraries (personal, commercial or from web) and the activities were clearly observed. Due to the geographical differences, we were only able to visit one of the local participant's studio personally and some other through video conferencing. It was also noticeable that each user tends to have their own workflow and sound management methodologies in their project. They seem to have efficient project management skills of adding tags, colors and particular naming conventions for audio files. Most of these functions were provided in the commercial sound management systems used by these users. The findings from these observations are more outlined in section 4.2.

- **Prototype evaluation** A personal evaluation of the participants were collected in complement with the results from pre/post-questionnaires.
- **About innovation** In this phase, we further asked their opinion about the need of open innovations and products in the domain to leverage audio content management systems in the creative industry. As part of AudioCommons[12] initiative, potential applications of the integrations of creative common licensed audio collections were also discussed.

In this interview sessions, various aspects of sound management systems were discussed openly. Several problems mentioned in the state of the art and user evaluation were identified to be on same page and various practical approaches were proposed by the participants itself. These aspects are further discussed in the next session.

4.2 Results Analysis

In this section, we outline our findings from the qualitative expert-user studies, interviews and the further quantitative data analysis on the used dataset. The results are structured into three categories even though all of them might be slightly overlapped each other conceptually.

Taxonomy

As mentioned in the section 2.1.1, taxonomical organization of sounds has been extensively studied and the recent developments in building broad categorization and ontologies such as AudioSet[9] shows some potential in organizing sounds inside audio production environments. Some participants made the following quotes when ask for desired features in their sound browsers during the pre-test questionnaire.

“Meaningful taxonomies”

“Hierarchical tags: nature would include water, forest, fire, animals; water would include river, rain, waves, ocean...”

“Possibility of more sounds, like a class query browsing”

These user statements points out the need structured content ans text-based semantic annotations to ease up the browsing process. Existing ontologies in [9] can be benefited in semantic tagging tasks from the timbral descriptors.

High-level timbral attributes

Among eight users, almost all of the users highly express the integration of the perceptual timbral feature browsing into their current sound browsing systems. However, overall the proposed system was only rated as average in comparing to the traditional sound browsers. This is probably because the absence of advance text-based retrieval in the prototype. An similar previous study [27] points out this solution.

The results of questions asking users to describe their ideal sound browser were also portrayed some interesting insights. The users say

“It gives you the opportunity of finding a fairly specific sound”

“I find brightness better (or are easier to interpret) and results in my opinion”

This results reassures the usability of *brightness* timbral feature in the commercial sound retrieval systems which was already explored in previous studies [7], [27], [40]

[41] etc. However there were comments by certain users who are dissatisfied by the brightness descriptor while dealing with highly dense and iterative sounds.

Another interesting observation was mentioning other relevant or desired perceptual timbral features by the users.

“It’s surprising why most of the DAW’s I use do not include this. I can think about browsers based on rhythm properties (meter, bpm, density, syncopation, or based on key or chord progression, BPM of course, or other higher level features describing timbre (inharmonicicity, noisiness, brightness, ..) and the sound quality (compressed, raw, musical/nonmusical, ...)”

However, expert-users also states their concern of integrating high-level feature to differentiate sounds with iterative and single events. The studies of morphological descriptions as in [18] [19], [25] etc can be utilized in solving these problems.

In respect to these studies, reliability of the timbral models should be studied with broad class of heterogeneous sound collections

“System and its interface are super cool easy to understand, but probably timbral models need to be improved”

We also find out that the timbral models used in the project output variable values for the same sound in different sampling rates. Further studies have to be conducted in order to investigate and solve this aspect of reliability of timbral models.

4.2.1 Interface

- **Simplicity** One of the general comment about the system interface from all the participants was the need of simplicity of the interface. During user studies an questions was asked about mentioning their favorite sound browsing tools. And, here are some of their testimonies.

“A mix between a great search engine, beautiful interface, endless sound sources.”

“I normally use SoundMiner beacuse of its easy integration with Protools and our local databases. It’s advanced meta-data management has been always been

helpful while dealing with big projects'

"I use AudioFinder to organize and browse my collection of field recordings. It allows tagging and batch renaming, among other things. This makes it much better than simple folders because I browse my sounds using various different overlapping criteria (location, time of day, trips I've made, natural vs urban...)"

"Native instruments Maschine. The browser use a taxonomy with 3 levels of depth, precise and not overwhelming"

All these answers point out to the assumption that most of the professional production houses prefer to have simple interfaces with various functions.

- **Visualization** Several users pointed out suggestions regarding the visualization aspect of the user interface.

"Loads of sounds titles with weird names. Makes the process boring."

A user commented the frustration of using list based results and especially in the case of collaborative sound collections where there is no naming conventions which results the occurrence of weird names.

"Really cool idea! Maybe when using multirank or multifilter you could show how the sounds are distributed in a 2D plane so that you can choose from the brightest and least rough to the roughest and least bright."

One of the expected results from the interface evaluation was about inadequacy of list-based 1-D browser. Some users suggested the use of multi-dimensional spaces for organizing the sounds. This have been studied over various studies in content-based audio retrieval ([40], [26], [38], [27], [41]).

Another user suggests a very useful suggestions regarding integrating visual cues maps to the availability of sounds in the database. Along with dynamic parameter allocation this feature can be intuitive for the user. This topic is more discussed in the next section.

"The search latency made me thing i was doing something wrong, but once notices is not critical. Id like to have sliders maybe filled with shades related

to the density of sounds at given value (just an idea). Its frustrating when no sounds found”

A not so expected opinion was also recorded, which suggests the options of hearing or seeing the sounds that have been filtered out by threshold based filtering approach use in the prototype.

“I liked the idea of using perceptual filters, but would still like to see the elements that are left out. When filtering by brightness, it is helpful to listen to non-bright sounds as well.”

As expected there were mixed opinions regarding the interface, while most of expert-users working in post-production prefers to have a simplified interface with more functions to control the search. On the other side, audio researchers, people with music production and DJing background propose the use of 2-D spaces for the interface and this reassures the study of [41]. Later in the in-depth interview sessions, some participants proposed the concept of 'switching-mode' to address the need both users. In this mode, a user can choose the layout of interface to and traditional list-based from multi-dimensional and vice-versa.

4.2.2 Search process

“The most frustrating thing is me, that I don't know what I'm looking for... but certainly it is a pain in the ass to search for the sound when I'm finally clear with the sound quality I'm after ! ”

In the case of search results there were some feedbacks as well from the expert-users. however, compare to other elements this is not so clear and hence some computation methods were used to find the underlying problems. There were mainly kind of search methods used in the search process

- **Threshold-based filtering** According to one user he prefer filtering approach since he is frustrated in auditioning long lists but at the same time his workflow well integrated with traditional systems.

“I prefer anything that uses less lists.”

One of the main problems raised in using threshold based filtering approach is the retrieval of less results or (sometime no results at all) at certain points in feature space. These problem again get multiplies when using multiple parameters since the dimensions of feature space also increases. Figure 28 shows the Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) plot of all four timbral attributes for all seven sound classes in the fs-amb-sfx-700 dataset.

Figure 28: KDE plot of all the timbral attributes (*brightness, hardness, depth, roughness*) for each 7 classes of sounds in the FS-AMB-SFX-700 dataset. Starting from up-most left to right, 1.Exploration, 2.Rubbing, 3.Gunshot, 4.Tearing, 5.Footsteps, 6.Rain and 7.Wind

From figure 28, it is very clear that different sound classes have different or similar timbral attribute distribution which makes a simple threshold-based filtering inadequate. Hence dynamic parameter allocation for different use

cases and sound classes can be utilized to obtain some results at every point in the feature space. A simple dynamic range allocation already has been implemented to the prototype system after the user evaluation.

- **Distance-based ranked sorting** In contrary to filter-based approach, distance-based ranked sorting helps when the user wants more results with relatively extreme range of feature values. Sometimes the users are lost in the ranked results since they are unaware of what is an exact close-match of attribute means. This seems to be confusing for some user in terms of perceptual relevance of the closely related sounds. More sophisticated ranking algorithms than normal euclidean distances should be applied and compare to obtain more refined results. As in filter-based approach, there is also an possibility dynamic parameter allocations using multi-variate feature interpolations. This could be undergone in the future works.

From the user ratings in the surveys, very least amount of rating were opted for *multiple slider-based ranked sorting* while *single fader-based filtering* and *single fader-based ranked sorting* obtained very high favorable ratings. *multiple slider-based filtering* has a average rating between the two extremes. However, these differences very subtle and need more sophisticated and quantitative studies to validate. From the in-depth interviews, there have been also suggestions including different combinations of features to dynamically update the query. As we have already explained, all these methods have their pros and cons which enable them to work well in a specific situation. Perhaps, an ideal way is to provide all the options and then let the user choose his workflow.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

5.1 Summary and Contribution

Our study argued that the use of perceptual timbral attributes can improve the audio retrieval and management process of non-musical ambiguous sound collections in audio production environments. Our main methodology of research was to develop a probe system to observe it's in a real context, then evaluate it and further inspire new ideas for research. A probe system was developed in order to gain further insights of the user needs. We integrated four high-level timbral feature models of (*brightness, depth, roughness and hardness*) for filtering and re-ranking the search results. Even though our work has been focused on retrieving ambiguous sound collections, We believe that the basic approach presented here works well for sound database management in audio production environments. In-depth user interviews and surveys provided much needed qualitative feedback on the usability of timbral features for filtering and ranking on various use-case scenarios. We had also identified certain problems in the topic from a expert-user point of view which gave some insights for future research and the potential of immediate application of these technologies in audio industry. We had outlined many ideas for the improvement of current systems which we are actively pursuing.

We have accomplished several tasks. Main contributions of thesis can be summarized

as follows:

- We developed an audio retrieval system incorporating high-level perceptual attributes (*brightness, depth, hardness, roughness*) for filtering and re-ranking the search results inside audio production pipelines.
- We proposed user-centric approach in developing sound retrieval and management systems in audio production environments using qualitative expert-user evaluation.
- Outputs from user studies and in-depth interviews with expert-users were used to identify potential future research and development guidelines in the topic.
- In context of AudioCommons project, our work can be utilized for building embeddable tools for integrating creative commons licensed databases to audio production environments.
- Freesound Max-MSP modules, a reusable modular client library of freesound API has been developed as a part of this thesis work. This will allow creative people to integrate freesound database in audio production environments without worrying about technical complexities.

However, the main problems in audio retrieval is that sometimes the users doesn't have a clear idea of what kind of sound they want or how they can describe the sound they want. On the another hand, when the users have a clear idea or description of the sound they want, there is are no technologies which leverages to achieve this task according to user's expectation.

From in-depth interviews and user studies we observed that audio professionals have distinguishable workflow in searching and choosing sound from databases. Each individuals might get self-trained in the workflow they are comfortable with. Perhaps, a ideal system should have the options to explore all the available possibilities of audio retrieval techniques which lets users to explore their sound collections in endless ways. Recent developments in MIR, machine learning and natural language

processing (NLP) are promising in solving these problems. Hence, we believe an hybrid approach in integrating these researchers in an common platform would be an first step in bridging the lack of innovative smart tools for sound management in the creative industries.

5.2 Future Work

Finally, we conclude our work by listing some immediate future directions to improve the system as guided from our evaluation studies and literature review.

- **Automatic semantic tagging based on timbral description** Some of our user interviews reveals their love for semantic text-based filters. In respect to this an subjective automatic semantic text tagging feature can be done based on the timbral attributes
- **Advanced dynamic parameter allocation and feature interpolation** Dynamic allocation of search parameters and muti-variate feature interpolation can be beneficial in obtaining constant search results and better user-experience, as observed from our study.
- **Dynamic audio previews** This feature retrieves and previews a relevant section of a sound file according to the timbral attribute values in the query. This might be computationally expensive when dealing with large sound databases and also should be studied.
- **Audio quality description** Integrating automatic audio quality description using audio content analysis and meta-data.
- **Spatial audio information** Integrating attributes constituting spatial description of sound. From in-depth interview sessions, we had observed that these features are crucial while designing sound for audio-viusal and interactive media such as movies and games (where sound management systems have high relevance).

- **Timbral models for Density** Timbral models that differentiate less impulsive and highly impulsive sounds.
- **Audio retrieval by ADSR envelopes** Attack, decay, sustain, release envelope parameters of a sound sample can be used for the retrieval process.
- **Experiments with more broader and big datasets**

5.3 Reproducibility

All the data, surveys, computer scripts and source-code of the system used for this research work is publicly available in github repositories^{1,2}. It comprises python scripts for downloading, pre-processing and analyzing the datasets. There are also python scripts for batch timbral feature extraction of audio files. The source-code of the developed prototype are also publicly. Check Appendix A. Online resources, for more information.

¹<https://github.com/albincorreya/smcmasterthesis2017>

²<https://github.com/albincorreya/PerceptualSoundBrowser>

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³<http://store.soundminer.com/>

⁴<http://www.icedaudio.com/site>

⁵<http://www.creativenetworkdesign.com/Main-Pages/NetMix-Pro.html>

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Appendix A

Online Resources

All the resources used in this research work has been uploaded to online public repositories. You can find the links to various resources below.

- **fs-amb-sfx-700 dataset :**

<https://github.com/albincorreya/smcmasterthesis2017/tree/master/fs-amb-sfx-700%20dataset>

- **Dataset builder (freesound text-search oauth2 downloader) :**

https://github.com/albincorreya/smcmasterthesis2017/blob/master/fs_text_search_oauth2

- **Batch feature-extraction scripts :**

https://github.com/albincorreya/smcmasterthesis2017/blob/master/multiclass_timbralfeature

- **Source code of the developed system :**

<https://github.com/albincorreya/PerceptualSoundBrowser>

- **Link to the online questionnaire :**

<https://goo.gl/forms/Fv9CCRiFi6MOUvRA3>

- **Link to demo video of the system :**

<https://vimeo.com/231350962>